

SOME PROBLEMS OF MODERN ANALYSIS OF THE CONTINUITY OF THE CONTENT OF THE PHYSICS COURSE PROGRAM OF THE SYSTEM OF GENERAL AND SECONDARY SPECIALIZED EDUCATION

Nurimbetov Kurbanbay Keunimjay ugli¹, Jaksimuratova

Zamira Jumabayevna², Janabergenova Gulnaz Jaksilikovna³

^{1,2,3} Masters degree of the Nukus State Pedagogical Institute Named After Ajiniyaz, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6299682>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th February 2022

Accepted: 15th February 2022

Online: 25th February 2022

KEY WORDS

general education, academic lyceum, physics, membership, educational standard, method.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses some of the current problems and solutions of the current period of analysis of the content of the course of physics in the system of general education.

The purpose of creating an updated systematic course of physics is to ensure the continuity of physics courses in existing general education schools and academic lyceums. If in the coming years advanced physics courses in these educational institutions are not brought to the level of education of the most developed countries, then in 5-10 years industrial enterprises of the republic will not have sufficient knowledge in these disciplines.

Analytical results of scientific and methodological, pedagogical, psychological, observational and scientific research with physics teachers in recent years confirm that physics is one of the subjects in which interest in general education schools and academic lyceums is declining. The control work carried out in general education schools, academic lyceums of the republic to determine the effectiveness of the

physics course, surveys, test results of students entering higher educational institutions showed the following:

- the level of assimilation by students of educational material, its application in practice is reduced;
- their interest in the study of physics decreases, the level of education, skills and specialization decreases;
- inability of students to apply the theoretical problems of the content of physical education in practice;
- It is quite obvious that views remain narrow, uncomplicated concepts.

That's why these physics instructs, the workshecue, while wide knowledge of the efficiency of the effuperation, the activity of students, loading into the practice of educatorsThe introduction of teaching methods to practice is not one of the important aspects of the current time.

The young psychologist and physiological properties of students in the existing direction are not. All students are not in a common interested study of their interests in the study of physical physicist. In the Mardums of the Nations without developed and some fostitaries, this problem has been a solution of these problems and have a fair of the textbook and textbook, with methods with methodical complexes necessary with methods of reading necessary textbooks and readings. 'Maltes. Based on the Uk Tajrizinen, the variability (parallel) direction and textbooks for academic lyceums (parallel) and widespread texture are the creative (parallel) directions and the widespread use. Compulsory educational institutions are based on the ability to provide Izshaking and continuous education on the basis of this standard and follow the standard and continuity, N.M.Shaxmaev In the author of D.Sh.Shodievs Reading Physics classes Hacde Collections repeat and their context is alignal. This methods of reading was a difference in exploring the achievements of world science in the methodical complex.

The importance of modern physical education in secondary schools and academic lyceums in society is growing, exerting a decisive influence on the development of the achievements of science and technology, general information about modern achievements in science, culture, technology and technology, as well as their place. in everyday life. [1]

That is why it is necessary to pay the main postal ITIB to develop rapidly in the world.The shores of the Ishashi education in this Education is, the formation of a state of logic and generalities, and the

knowledge of the national and general Insaaniy, Haden socialityKnowledge necessary for life and continuing to continue learning is necessary.

Mandatory education institutions Barshe Physics education Barifi Barifi Lots of teaching.The main focus of the main focus is on the tintenance of tier physical education of general physics education, and without these without these, Kúntge results will not be achieved in education.

Physics education General Secondary Schools, Students Education in Academy Lyceums Barshe Students Describe them 2-3 ways to explain to them in 2-3 ways.

In order to fulfill the urgent tasks set for the content of modern physical education in the above educational institutions, it is necessary to take into account the need to prepare students on the basis of professional development, human development, life development, technical and technical progress. Materials should be included.

Currently, the losses of the torment of physical education are taught in various academic lyceums. In the group, general education schools, the academy does not mean that the academy Lyceumsoding does not mean the beginning of general. Therefore, mutacca interest in security and loss they need to learn from the researcher to educate this tree. This does not require any changes to teaching compartment and responsibilities, i.e. Maintain the education of physics is carried out. Expanding the information and formulations, not to expand the laws and formulas, maybe learning material, learning the reading material, to learn Hadenire literature, learners of learning in textbooks to learn Terirshe literature ' Attempted the period based on the submission of materials for

the sure reflections, we can win the use of pedagogical technologies.

Especially in these educational institutions, doctors of the pedagogical sciences is to study the following opinion: ie how to teach academic lyceums in academic lyceums. Billeseing for the physical significance of students in physics or to be inappropriate to be practiced in physics, are insignificant to the mathematical meaning of it. These career institutions are not when they give physics education special rible, but is to educate the educated learners. [2]

General education schools and academy lyceums The teacher is very interesting to explain to each person of the modern technical technology as a modernized knowledge as a present-day acquaintance.

The main specialized training school of education at the General Secondary Schools of Education of Education IBarak is to worry the passion for lifelongs. The material learned to improve the interesting material will be explanted to the educationals, depending on the moreajrabege. Therefore, at IMKAN, these education institutions are physics teaching to multiply physical tajiyiger in textbilization and feed on the main workshop IMIBD to improve their supply. Organization of Physic Tajriybe, very defilious and hardshipal education and lyceum education educator Updated physics lyceum reader Reading Damonstracion Tajriyerdiybe, not preparation of the main focus in placing their physical Tajiyiger Its the following, migratory physical tajiybenin idea, maxi, function Ladiring Her Important Readers Language.

Underly evolving development of scientific technical technology, great changes in the unprecedentedly emiscatory and daily lives will lead to the absence of occupations and specialists. This is to create toilet the scientific level of the student of the student of the student of this educational institutions. Mathematics do not have mathematics in the scientific dimension of bore physics. When revealing the importance of physical events, the stallion of mathematics is given great, to explain the meaning of your physical events, should not be given to excess mathematography. It does not allow Eshh to understand the content of people close to a person in the learning of the formulas.

General secondary schools and academy lyceums Strive in teaching the basics of physics, the reading material to explain in the science industry. In explaining the material reading, it is a simple convenient use of similar methods that are simple comfortable for students, with common ground conditions in common.

Compulsory educational institutions updated physics education is the head of physics, As OKI higher educational institutions not leasing not to be abbreviated. Physics functions Lets vary with wanger brackling.

Secondary schools and academy lyceums are hitting a very large chosen reading material from the total physics course. The width of the reading material should be accomplished in Ibarat, many Costs in the study process. Therefore, when this education is selecting a Physics Department of Physics, the main ITIbridge is primarily the main ITIBCe to comment on the following points:

- Harmony of pedagogical machinet;

- Importing of practice;
- description of the selected material for students;

Dirylers who claimed this are first considerable thoughts that have other important opinions.

Pedagogical Maxcetke's concurrence:

- The development of the general education of the reading material, that is, the scientific eyes of students - development of thinking of the examination and logic thinking;
- Phaniographic techniques for students, explaining knowledge related to the assumptions and legitiments of the main leisure;
- They include national general Insan values, the formation of a consciousness of the nationality, as well as the formation of and uplifting.

Practical value, the importance of the selected educational material and the need for its compliance with modern requirements when choosing professions and skills, the importance of polytechnic knowledge, modern computer technology.

The scientific procedure of the selected reading material is the strength of the selected material and compulsory educational institutions of the content of physics is understood correct content structure.

The selected material is understood with the understanding of the explanatory levels, the readiness of many teachers and the level of training of teaching and teaching methods Hazde. [3]

This knowledge is included in the content of the updated physics education, which is mandatory for all learners to learn, and additional material can be included in order to understand them to fasten the defined material.

Curriculum development of the rapid development of modern technologies, these educational institutions fulfill great importance in the content of physics, on the practice of physical education, which are relevant to the practice of physics. Therefore, for this education institutions are important to show the general politneci directions, not by industry in the teaching of the physics, not to the use of physical education in physics.

Compulsory education institutions are the connection of imkanies as the basic ITIB in physics is the science of reading physics education.

The importance of mathematics is marked in physics. Bishrq in these educational institutions Discover the physics and deep content of the physics in teaching the content of physics is needed to make mathematical maths mathematics mathematics.

In secondary schools and academic lyceums, there is no need to explain the physical phenomena of learning in the context of physics courses. In this regard, it is appropriate to be guided by the following views of the Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor Davron Chodiev:

"Incoming physical formulas will never be able to get acquainted with any people close to students ... The second level is secondary schools, most general secondary schools, the academy of academy lyceums, understand the meaning and meaning of the physical event of the academy". This thought is to cite an example of the main specific summary schools and academic lyceums, as the result of the revelation of mathsatical orientation. Frequent Physical Mathematical Dedic Dashtillis and

Calculation The main content of secondary schools and academy lyceum is not tossed before you have the physical content of the

basic student event, it is not a means of appearance. There are no succeeds in this tool.

REFERENCES:

1. "Ilmiy tatqiqotlar sammiti 2022" kóp tarmoqli ilmiy sammit materiallari toplami. 2022 yil.
2. M.Djoraev. Fizika o`qitish metodikasi. – T.: "Abu matbuot – konsalt", 2015.-170 b.
3. M.Djoraev. Fizika o`qitishda statistik g'oyalar. – T.: "O`qituvchi", 1996.-26 b.